

UNLOCKING WEB HISTORIES: LEVERAGING LLMs AND RAG TO TRANSFORM DISCOVERY IN WEB ARCHIVES

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Abstract – This paper explores how Large Language Models (LLMs) and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) can be applied to improve access to web archives. These collections are often difficult to navigate due to their complexity and the limitations of traditional search tools. The author examines how RAG can help address concerns around trust and transparency in AI by grounding LLM outputs in external, curated sources. At the University of Victoria Libraries, a custom RAG pipeline was developed to build on tools like WARC-GPT. This pipeline enables natural language querying with source attribution and incorporates optimizations in data preprocessing, chunking strategies, and hardware acceleration. When tested on real-world web archives of cultural significance, it demonstrated improved retrieval accuracy and computational efficiency. The discussion also considers the broader implications for digital preservation in an age of uncertainty, emphasizing the importance of trust, ethics, sustainability, and continued human oversight in AI-powered discovery. The findings suggest that RAG offers a promising way to unlock the value of underused digital heritage collections while upholding the foundational values of research libraries, including long-term preservation, equitable access, and responsible stewardship of historic materials.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In a time of heightened global uncertainty, political unrest, and widespread disinformation, the need for trustworthy information is more critical than ever. Research libraries and archives, as long-standing guardians of knowledge, are exploring the potential of large language models (LLMs) to support digital preservation and improve access to born-digital collections. LLMs are a type of deep neural network trained on massive text datasets using transformer architectures [1], and they are beginning to reshape how libraries manage digital workflows and access to unique digital collections. These systems show promise in automating some tasks such as transcribing archival content, extracting entities, and generating metadata that requires significant human effort [2]. At their best, LLMs improve efficiency and make preservation and access work more accessible. At their worst, they generate convincing but false information and operate as opaque systems that resist explanation. As research libraries adopt LLMs, a key question emerges: how can we apply these technologies to enhance access and preservation while ensuring the integrity and reliability of our systems?

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is emerging as a promising approach to address concerns around trust and transparency in AI, especially in systems powered by large language models and unsupervised deep learning techniques. Rather than relying solely on the internal training data

of a large language model, RAG systems are built to retrieve information from external, curated sources, such as institutional repositories, digital archives, and other high-value research library collections. These collections are not only rich in scholarly and cultural significance but also reflect the carefully maintained priorities and expertise of the institutions that steward them. By grounding responses in real, verifiable documents, RAG offers a critical alternative to the inscrutable and often untraceable outputs of standalone language models, reinforcing transparency, accountability, and scholarly integrity.

The technical process behind RAG is both powerful and elegant. Digital collections are first transformed into high-dimensional vector spaces, allowing the system to identify and retrieve semantically relevant materials at the moment a query is made. These retrieved documents are then passed to the language model, which uses them to generate a response. The result is a conversational interface backed by real evidence: a tool that not only answers questions, but also points users directly to the sources behind those answers. This method opens the door to a new kind of engagement with digital collections. Instead of static databases or keyword search tools, RAG enables dynamic, exploratory access. This has particular promise for web archives, which are among the most underused resources in our digital heritage landscape.

Despite their immense value, web archives remain notoriously difficult to navigate. WARC (Web ARChive) files often demand specialized tools and technical expertise just to access them, and even then, traditional keyword searches frequently fall short. The content itself is messy, cluttered with boilerplate code, visual noise, broken links, and duplicate content. As a result, even the richest collections can feel inaccessible, limiting their use in research and diminishing their visibility within broader discovery systems.

This is where Retrieval-Augmented Generation offers real promise. By pairing RAG with web archives, libraries and archives can begin to surface the real value hidden within. Instead of asking researchers to sift through a kind of digital rubble, we can offer intuitive, context-aware access that makes these collections not only searchable, but genuinely usable. That's the vision, at least. As we'll see, realizing it comes with significant challenges.

This paper focuses on applying RAG to web archives, specifically through a custom pipeline built at the University of Victoria (UVic) Libraries. The UVic

Libraries' custom RAG pipeline was designed to "unlock" WARC-based collections by enabling natural language querying with source-attributed results, thus supporting discovery and trust in these complex born-digital records. We present the technical architecture of this pipeline, the optimizations that improve its performance over an existing tool (WARC-GPT), and discuss implications for digital preservation in an age of uncertainty.

The paper is structured as follows. The *Background* section introduces key concepts related to large language models, Retrieval-Augmented Generation, and previous work, including WARC-GPT. The *Methods* section describes the architecture of the custom RAG pipeline and the optimizations implemented to improve performance. In the *Results* section, we compare this pipeline to WARC-GPT, highlighting gains in retrieval accuracy and computational efficiency. The *Discussion* section considers the broader implications for libraries and digital preservation, including questions of trust, ethical use, computational demands, and long-term sustainability. Finally, the *Conclusion* reflects on the evolving role of RAG and LLMs in digital preservation and access and emphasizes the ongoing importance of human oversight and critical engagement.

II. BACKGROUND

LLMs AND THE NEED FOR RETRIEVAL AUGMENTATION IN LIBRARIES

Recent advances in foundational language models, such as GPT-4, have created new opportunities for working with large, unstructured digital collections. These models can generate fluent, natural language responses and answer questions by identifying patterns in massive training datasets. Libraries and archives have started to explore the potential of LLMs to support digital preservation and access activities, including metadata generation, content analysis, and description.

At the same time, using LLMs in preservation work introduces significant risks. One major concern is the problem of hallucination, where models produce false or misleading information that sounds authoritative. This is especially problematic in archives and libraries, where accuracy, provenance, and trust are central to our work. As Jones points out, hallucinations may never be fully eliminated, but their impact can be reduced through careful system design [3].

Another challenge is the lack of transparency in how LLMs generate their responses. These systems are often difficult to interpret, which complicates efforts to explain, verify, or audit their behavior. In settings where reliable access to knowledge is essential, this opacity raises important questions about accountability and trust.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation seeks to tackle these issues by grounding LLM outputs in external evidence. In a RAG pipeline, the LLM is not expected to know everything; instead, it retrieves relevant documents from a collection at inference time and uses that content (called *context* in a RAG pipeline) to formulate answers [4]. This approach has two major benefits for libraries and archives. First, *domain specificity*: the system can leverage specialized local collections (often missing from the LLM's general training data) to answer niche or institutionally relevant queries [5]. Second, *source attribution*: retrieved documents can be cited, allowing users to trace the response back to trustworthy sources [6]. By design, a RAG system can display the snippets of archived content that informed an answer, fostering transparency and user confidence in an age of uncertainty, where AI-generated outputs often lack verifiability [7].

Early implementations of RAG in cultural heritage contexts have demonstrated both the potential and the limitations of this approach. One notable example is WARC-GPT, an open-source tool developed by the Harvard Library Innovation Lab and released in early 2024 [8]. WARC-GPT applies RAG techniques to web archive files, allowing users to pose questions in natural language instead of relying on keyword searches or navigating thousands of archived pages manually. The system performs multi-document semantic search across a collection of WARC files, retrieves relevant segments, and uses a large language model to generate summaries or answers.

A key feature of WARC-GPT is its support for source attribution. Each answer includes the originating WARC record and an excerpt of the retrieved content, making it possible for users to verify the information against the original archived page. This design promotes transparency and helps build trust, offering a more accessible and intuitive entry point into web archives for researchers and the public.

WARC-GPT is an impressive and thoughtfully constructed tool that represents a significant step forward in applying RAG to unique digital collections. It demonstrates how large language models can support

conversational access to web archives and serves as a valuable foundation for further experimentation. It also highlights important challenges that must be addressed when applying AI in a research library setting.

While WARC-GPT performed well in many areas, our testing surfaced several issues related to retrieval accuracy, contextual relevance, and preprocessing of noisy data. To explore these issues more deeply, we developed a custom RAG pipeline designed specifically for our collections and infrastructure. Many of the enhancements we implemented—such as improved HTML text extraction, tailored chunking strategies, and hardware-aware optimization—could be added to WARC-GPT through further configuration and customizations. However, our goal was to build something bespoke, not only to improve performance, but also to gain a deeper understanding of how each component contributes to the system as a whole.

Creating a custom pipeline allowed us to experiment with different approaches, evaluate trade-offs, and build a system we could deploy and maintain locally with confidence. This hands-on development process was instrumental in helping us learn more about the mechanics of RAG and its implications for access to unique digital collections.

Our experience with WARC-GPT also revealed challenges that influenced the design of our system. Web archives contain complex and often messy data. A single WARC file may include HTML content, JavaScript, navigation menus, advertisements, and other non-essential elements. Ingesting this content without filtering can introduce irrelevant or duplicated material into the vector index, which in turn can reduce retrieval quality and lead to fragmented or inaccurate answers. We observed that some responses were incomplete or included hallucinated content not present in the source documents.

Scalability was another important consideration. Generating embeddings for large web archive collections proved to be time-consuming and resource-intensive, sometimes requiring several days to weeks of processing. These constraints raise concerns about how such systems can be kept current when new crawls are added. In addition, although WARC-GPT can be deployed using open-source tools, it often depends on access to external LLM services or computational infrastructure that may not be feasible for smaller institutions. These issues point to broader questions around sustainability, autonomy, and the

long-term viability of AI-enhanced discovery systems in libraries and archives.

Despite these limitations, WARC-GPT offered important benefits. It enabled exploratory, conversational search across a complex web archive collection, something that traditional tools struggle to support. Its citation feature also ensured that users could trace outputs back to their sources, reinforcing trust and accountability. These outcomes suggest that, with further refinement, RAG could become a valuable tool for making archived web content more accessible and useful, while continuing to uphold the principles of authenticity and transparency that are central to digital preservation.

DIGITAL PRESERVATION IN AN AGE OF UNCERTAINTY

The context for this work is the broader challenge of digital preservation in an age of uncertainty. Rapidly evolving technologies such as artificial intelligence offer new opportunities to enhance digital preservation, while also introducing significant challenges to established principles. Tools like RAG can provide more intuitive access to large, unstructured collections and support automated metadata generation, potentially helping institutions manage the scale and complexity of born-digital content [9]. However, these benefits are accompanied by new uncertainties related to transparency, bias, sustainability, and the long-term usability of AI systems.

In archival and library contexts, where provenance, context, and authenticity are essential, these uncertainties raise many questions. How can we ensure that AI-mediated retrieval preserves the original meaning of records? What are the ethical implications if an AI system misrepresents, distorts, or selectively surfaces information? And from a preservation standpoint, what happens when today's vector indexes and language models become obsolete? Will future systems be able to interpret or reproduce the results generated by today's tools?

Library and archives professionals are responding to these concerns with thoughtful strategies. Institutional frameworks such as the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) AI Guidelines and the Ontario Council of University Libraries (OCUL) position paper on artificial intelligence emphasize trust, transparency, and human oversight as foundational principles for responsible AI adoption [10]. These values have guided our own work. We view the RAG pipeline not as a

replacement for traditional finding aids, discovery tools, or human curatorial expertise, but as a supplementary tool that can support discovery while maintaining the integrity, provenance, and interpretive context of materials.

By grounding responses in the authentic source materials of our collections, we aim to enhance access while preserving trust. In the sections that follow, we describe how we built and optimized our RAG pipeline to reflect these priorities. We evaluate its performance in comparison with prior approaches, including WARC-GPT, and consider how such systems might be sustainably integrated into digital preservation and collections practices amid the uncertainties of AI's future.

III. METHODS

CUSTOM RAG PIPELINE ARCHITECTURE

To address the limitations observed with WARC-GPT and tailor a solution for Uvic Libraries, we developed a bespoke RAG pipeline using a streamlined, mostly open-source toolchain. Figure 1 presents an overview of the pipeline architecture.

Figure 1: Pipeline Architecture

At a high level, the pipeline consists of the following components: (1) Data ingestion and preprocessing, (2) Vector embedding and storage, and (3) LLM-based query answering with retrieval augmentation. We describe each stage below, highlighting optimizations introduced at each step.

Data Collection & Cleaning: Rather than ingesting raw WARC files directly, which include all content (HTML, scripts, etc.), we first extract only the meaningful textual content from the archived web pages. We used `wget` to fetch the archived HTML pages from the WARC collection and BeautifulSoup (a Python HTML parsing library) to scrape primary text content while filtering out navigation menus, advertisements, and other non-informative elements. Specifically, the parser was configured to capture content from `<p>` tags, headings, and other central HTML elements, ignoring scripts, style tags, and repetitive boilerplate. We also applied regular expressions to remove residual markup or noisy patterns (e.g. URL templates, duplicate footer text) and to normalize whitespace. This cleaner data pipeline ensures that only

semantically relevant text (the substance of each page) proceeds to the indexing stage. By dramatically reducing noise in the input, we aim to produce embeddings that represent the actual informational content of the collection, thereby improving retrieval quality.

Document Chunking & Embeddings: After text extraction, each source document (e.g. an archived web page) is split into chunks suitable for the embedding model's input size. We experimented with various chunk sizes and overlap strategies to balance context richness against index size and search performance. Ultimately, we settled on chunks of ~512 tokens with a 50-token overlap between consecutive chunks. This window size was chosen based on empirical testing that showed larger chunks did not significantly improve answer quality but did bloat the vector store, whereas smaller chunks risked losing context. The 512-token chunks capture a few paragraphs of text each, which is usually sufficient for the LLM to understand context when answering questions. Each chunk is then converted into a vector embedding using a transformer-based embedding model. We used the open-source `Intfloat/e5-large-v2` model, a state-of-the-art sentence embedding model from Hugging Face, chosen for its strong performance on semantic textual similarity tasks [11]. This model generates a high-dimensional vector of 1024 dimensions for each text chunk, such that semantically similar chunks lie close together in the vector space. All chunk embeddings are stored in a local vector database (ChromaDB), which not only enables fast and efficient similarity search, but also provides robust support for storing and querying rich metadata alongside each embedding, making it easier to filter, organize, and retrieve results based on contextual information like source file, timestamp, or document type. We configured the vector index to use an Approximate Nearest Neighbors (ANN) method—specifically, Hierarchical Navigable Small World (HNSW) graphs—for scalable and efficient retrieval. The result of this stage is a searchable index of the archive's contents, where each entry is a cleaned text chunk mapped to its originating WARC page and collection metadata.

System Prompts and Prompt Engineering: System prompts play a critical role in shaping how large language models interpret and respond to queries. LLMs are known to be brittle: small changes in prompt wording can lead to substantial variations in output quality [12]. This sensitivity makes prompt engineering

a key component of any RAG-based system. In our implementation, we observed that including extensive instructions or system-level prompts directly in the user query can introduce noise during vector search. Because the user query is embedded and compared against the source document vector store, these additional tokens can distort the semantic signature of the query and reduce retrieval precision. To avoid this, we adopted a two-part prompting strategy. We kept the user query clean for embedding and similarity search, and then applied internal system prompts only at the generation stage. This ensures that retrieval is based solely on the user's intent, while the LLM is still guided to use the retrieved documents faithfully and avoid hallucination. The system prompt instructs the model to answer using only the provided sources and to cite them explicitly, reinforcing transparency and trust in the responses. We also note that the effectiveness of prompts can vary significantly across models. Different LLMs may require different prompt templates, structures, or constraints to perform reliably. To address this variability and support more robust prompt engineering across models, we are exploring tools such as DSPy, a framework from Stanford that allows developers to define, test, and optimize prompts programmatically across different LLM backends [13]. This modular approach may be particularly useful in library and archive contexts, where institutions may shift between hosted APIs and open-source local models over time.

LLM Query Interface: The retrieval-augmented query answering component ties everything together. We implemented a simple API and user interface (using Python Flask) where a user can submit a natural language question. Upon receiving a query, the system embeds the query with the same Intfloat/e5 model, then performs a similarity search in the ChromaDB vector store to fetch the top relevant chunks (typically the top n results, where $n = 5$ in most of our testing). These retrieved text chunks (along with their source identifiers) are then concatenated with the user's question to form an augmented prompt, which is sent to a Large Language Model. In our prototype, we used OpenAI's GPT-4 via API for the answer generation step. GPT-4 was prompted to answer the question using the provided chunks and to explicitly cite the sources (e.g. by including an identifier or snippet reference) in its answer. The model's response is finally returned to the user, accompanied by the source citations which link back to the archived pages. Notably, the architecture is modular: one could substitute a

different LLM (including open-source models hosted locally) for GPT-4, and similarly one could use a different vector database or embedding model as needed. This flexibility is important for local infrastructure and sustainability, as it allows future adaptation (for example, running entirely on-premises with an open LLM if API costs or privacy or security policies become an issue).

To optimize performance, we also took advantage of hardware acceleration during the indexing process. The embedding generation was parallelized and run on a machine with an Apple Silicon M3 GPU, which significantly sped up the otherwise time-consuming task of embedding thousands of chunks. By combining cleaner data and GPU acceleration, we brought the indexing time for our test collection down from about a week (with the original WARC-GPT approach on CPU) to only a few hours. This improvement suggests that relatively large web archive collections could be processed within practical time frames given appropriate use of modern hardware.

TEST COLLECTION AND EVALUATION PROCEDURE

To evaluate our custom RAG pipeline, we selected a web archive of the *Bob's Burgers Wiki*, a fan-maintained site documenting characters, episodes, lore, and plotlines from the animated television series [14]. While this might seem like an unconventional choice for a case study, it served several important purposes.

First, the collection represents a relatively self-contained but textually rich domain, making it ideal for controlled testing. The site includes a structured yet informal knowledge base with many interlinked pages, varying writing styles, and semi-consistent formatting, all characteristics that mirror challenges found in real-world archival web content. Second, the author's strong familiarity with the subject matter allowed us to evaluate the accuracy of responses directly, without the need for external datasets or specialized domain expertise. This allowed for more reliable comparisons of retrieval quality, hallucination rates, and citation fidelity across different systems. Finally, the collection exemplifies a type of user-generated cultural documentation that libraries and archives are increasingly interested in preserving. Fan wikis, like the *Bob's Burgers Wiki*, are part of our broader born-digital cultural record, and testing AI tools on such collections helps us anticipate how similar pipelines might perform on more traditional archival holdings.

Using this collection, we compared the performance of our bespoke RAG pipeline against

WARC-GPT. Key evaluation dimensions included:

- **Index size and efficiency:** We measured the total size of the vector store and embedding files, as well as the time required to build each system's index from the cleaned archive data.
- **Response quality:** We created a set of test questions covering both general and obscure knowledge (e.g., "What is Teddy's favorite hammer?" or "Who is the coach of the Golden Dragons?"). For each question, we assessed whether the system produced an accurate, complete, and coherent answer, and whether it correctly cited the relevant sources.
- **Retrieval relevance:** We examined the retrieved chunks to determine whether they contained the necessary information to support the LLM's answer. This helped us isolate issues related to retrieval from those related to the generation step.
- **System usability and performance:** We measured latency and monitored for operational issues during inference. Although accuracy and trustworthiness were primary concerns, responsiveness is also critical for practical deployment in research environments.

Through this evaluation, we aimed to test the robustness of the system in a semi-structured, culturally meaningful domain and to explore the practical implications of RAG pipelines for web archive access and digital preservation.

IV. RESULTS

PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENTS OVER WARC-GPT

Our custom RAG pipeline demonstrated clear improvements in both retrieval precision and computational efficiency compared to the baseline WARC-GPT setup. It is worth emphasizing that WARC-GPT is a highly flexible and well-designed framework. Many of the enhancements we implemented, such as improved text extraction, customized chunking, and optimized embedding workflows, could also be achieved within WARC-GPT through configuration and extension. Our decision to build a separate, purpose-built system was motivated by a desire to better understand the underlying components and to develop a pipeline that could be confidently deployed and maintained within our local infrastructure.

1. Cleaner Data, Better Retrieval: The preprocessing step yielded dramatically cleaner text chunks, which in turn improved the relevance of retrieval. We found that WARC-GPT's index often contained a great deal of "semantic noise." For example, many retrieved chunks were just navigation menus or repetitive page headers, which contributed nothing to answering a query. In contrast, the bespoke pipeline's index, built from custom filtered content, returned chunks with much higher semantic density. In a side-by-side comparison, a query for 'Teddy's hammer' returned irrelevant menu text from WARC-GPT's index, while our pipeline retrieved a meaningful paragraph from an article discussing the related episode of the series. This directly led to more informative answers. Anecdotally, for niche questions that WARC-GPT struggled with, the bespoke system was able to find and cite the needed information. For instance, when asked about the nature of Bob Belcher's rivalry with Jimmy Pesto, WARC-GPT often returned generic or incomplete responses that referenced episode listings or unrelated character summaries. In contrast, our custom pipeline retrieved specific paragraphs from character and episode pages that detailed the rivalry across multiple seasons, including direct quotes and properly cited excerpts from the relevant archived wiki entries.

2. Reduced Hallucinations and Improved Answer Quality: By grounding the LLM in higher-quality retrieved context, the bespoke pipeline produced more accurate and coherent answers. In our tests, WARC-GPT occasionally included extraneous or made-up details (hallucinations), especially if the top retrieved chunks were off-target. Our pipeline had a lower incidence of such errors. Both systems used the same underlying LLM for generation (GPT-4 in our case), so differences in output quality can be attributed to differences in the retrieval stage. The experiment confirmed that cleaning the input data and tuning chunking parameters greatly improves the signal-to-noise ratio of the context given to the LLM, which mitigates hallucinations by keeping the model focused on relevant, real content. Additionally, our pipeline was configured to always cite sources for factual statements, which helped us identify if an answer was unsupported (the LLM would explicitly say if it didn't find information).

3. Order-of-Magnitude Efficiency Gains: One of the starkest improvements was in the size and speed of the system. The original WARC-GPT index for the test collection (which naively embedded entire WARCs) was

over 10 GB in size. Our optimized vector store occupied only 240 MB for the same collection. This ~40× reduction in storage is explained by the aggressive filtering of non-content and the elimination of redundant text. A smaller index not only saves storage costs but also improves query latency; similarity searches over the 240 MB index were noticeably faster than over the 10 GB index. In terms of indexing time, WARC-GPT's embedding process took over a week (running on a CPU-only environment) for this collection. With the combination of data optimizations and GPU-accelerated embeddings, our pipeline processed the entire collection in under 5 hours. This suggests that even scaling to much larger web archive corpora could be feasible with our approach. The increased efficiency also opens the door to more frequent re-indexing or updates; for instance, if new WARC files are added to the collection, they could be integrated on a faster cycle.

Overall, these results indicate that the technical optimizations made to our RAG pipeline had a clear and positive impact. By focusing on data quality and processing efficiency, we improved not only the system's performance but also its practical value. The answers it generates are more likely to be accurate and are consistently linked to verifiable source material. This traceability supports the level of trust and transparency that is essential in research settings.

V. DISCUSSION

ENHANCING DISCOVERY AND TRUST IN DIGITAL COLLECTIONS

Our experiment underscores that when built with care, retrieval-augmented LLM systems can significantly enhance discovery in complex digital collections. The ability to ask nuanced questions and get direct answers (with references) transforms the user's interaction with preserved web content. Instead of wading through countless webpages or relying solely on metadata search or URL matches, researchers can engage in a dialogue with the collection. This more natural mode of access can unveil connections and information that might be missed in traditional retrieval methods.

Crucially, by grounding answers in the collection's own documents, the RAG approach helps maintain trust in an environment where AI is often (and rightly) met with skepticism. The system's design insists that every answer be supported by evidence from the archives, addressing the black box problem by allowing users to "check the AI's work" via citations. In the context of digital preservation, where we are

custodians of authentic records, this feature is not just a convenience but an ethical requirement. It ensures the AI does not become an authoritative voice on its own, but rather a conduit to the preserved knowledge. By providing verifiable answers, the system reduces uncertainty about the information's origin and reliability, thereby fostering greater user confidence in digital archives augmented with AI.

At the same time, the limitations and risks of such systems must be clearly acknowledged. While RAG can mitigate hallucinations, it does not eliminate them entirely, nor does it guarantee that the retrieval will surface all relevant facts. We observed that if information was not present in the collection (or if it was inadequately indexed), the system could still give incomplete answers. In those cases, the LLM might respond with "I do not have information on that" or could potentially stitch together an answer from partial context (though with our strict prompt instructions, it usually abstained rather than hallucinated). This highlights that RAG is only as good as the underlying collection and index. If a collection is biased or lacks certain perspectives, the answers will reflect that. There is a risk that users unfamiliar with the collection could take an AI-generated answer as comprehensive, when in fact it may omit aspects that were not in the data. Hence, transparency about the dataset and the AI's scope remains important.

Another aspect of trust is ensuring the integrity and provenance of the data feeding the AI. Our pipeline uses local processing of data, which means the content remains under the library's control (we did not, for instance, send entire WARC files to a third-party service for indexing). The only component involving an external service was the use of OpenAI's API for GPT-4, which meant snippets of archived text and the query were sent to an external server to generate the answer. In a production scenario, libraries would need to weigh this trade-off: using a proprietary model like GPT-4 can yield excellent answers, but it raises questions about data privacy (especially if source content is sensitive) and ongoing cost. An alternative is to run an open-source model locally using a platform like Ollama. While open models may not yet match GPT-4 in quality, the gap is closing rapidly. Running everything locally would enhance data sovereignty and ensure that the preservation process itself (including access tools) is sustainable. It's encouraging that WARC-GPT and our pipeline are flexible in this regard; for example, WARC-GPT can be configured to use only open-source components, from the vector DB to the LLM.

TRADE-OFFS AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR DEPLOYMENT

Our findings lead to several considerations that any library or archive should keep in mind when adopting RAG systems:

Infrastructure and Scalability: Even with optimizations, RAG pipelines are computationally intensive. Building embeddings for large collections requires powerful hardware (GPUs) or significant time. Libraries must plan for this, possibly by using cloud-based GPUs or dedicating local machines for indexing. The maintenance of a vector index also introduces a new kind of digital object to preserve (the index itself might need periodic re-generation as software improves, or migration as technologies evolve). Ensuring the system scales—in terms of both adding new data and supporting multiple simultaneous queries—is essential if it's to be a reliable service.

Data Quality and Preparation: A clear lesson is that time invested in data cleaning and preparation is rewarded with much better results. Institutions should assess their web archive data and possibly preprocess it (e.g. removing boilerplate, deduplicating pages, extracting text) before feeding it to any AI system. Not only does this improve accuracy, it also reduces storage and processing burdens. Data curation remains a cornerstone of digital preservation, even in AI-augmented scenarios.

Ethical and Legal Concerns: Using LLMs on preserved content can raise novel issues. For instance, if an archive contains copyrighted material, does providing AI-mediated summaries or answers from it constitute fair use? There may also be privacy implications if archives include personal data and the AI exposes it out of context. Ethically, we must ensure that the AI does not distort the historical record. If it creates a convincing but false narrative, users might be misled about the past. Implementing RAG with strict citation and perhaps limits on how it can combine information can help mitigate this. Many of these issues are being actively discussed in the preservation community, and guidelines are starting to form (e.g., ethical frameworks from professional organizations) emphasizing accountability and the continued role of human experts in reviewing AI outputs.

Sustainability and Future Access: Introducing AI tools into preservation workflows raises the question of how to preserve the tools themselves. If researchers in 2035 look back and wonder how an answer was generated, will we have preserved the version of the model or the index used? This is an open area for exploration. For now, treating the RAG system as a

black box that aids access (but is not itself preserved) is acceptable, but as these become part of scholarly workflows, we might need strategies to archive the AI's behavior or at least document it thoroughly. From a practical perspective, an open-source pipeline like ours is advantageous for sustainability: all components (except the optional use of GPT-4) are open and can be archived or (at least in theory) re-run in the future if needed. This reduces reliance on a single vendor or platform, aligning with the preservation principle of minimizing dependencies on volatile external services.

THE HUMAN-IN-THE-LOOP IMPERATIVE

One consistent theme is that human expertise remains essential. Our RAG pipeline can be seen as a sophisticated search tool: it amplifies what a researcher, librarian, or archivist can do, but it does not replace their judgment. In fact, we envision its best use as a collaborative system: a human asks questions, the AI retrieves and summarizes, and the human then interprets, verifies, and possibly asks refined follow-up questions. This iterative process can surface insights quickly, but at each step the human steers the inquiry and ensures that the answers make sense. In our experiments, having domain knowledge was useful to catch when the AI's answer was missing a nuance; a subject expert could then refine the query or go directly to the cited sources to gather more details. Encouraging this kind of engagement (rather than passive acceptance of AI outputs) will be important in training users and staff to work with these tools.

Our findings echo a broader point noted by library technologists: the future of research and preservation will be driven by the interplay between human expertise and machine intelligence, not by AI alone. The Association of Research Libraries emphasizes this balance in its guiding principles, stating that "no human, no AI" should underpin decision-making in library contexts [15]. Similarly, scholars have argued that the evolving landscape of information management "will require the integration of the expertise of human librarians with the intelligence of machines" [16].

Embracing AI is worthwhile precisely because it can augment human capabilities (speed, scale, pattern recognition) while humans provide oversight, context, and ethical guidance. The challenge is designing systems and workflows that leverage the best of both. RAG is a step in that direction, offering an explainable and controllable interface for LLMs. But it must be implemented with careful thought to integration: for

instance, archivists might use RAG results as a starting point to create or enhance finding aids, rather than giving end-users direct chat access without any mediation. There is a spectrum of possible use cases, from internal tooling (where staff use the system to help answer reference questions or process collections) to public-facing discovery systems. Each use case might have different requirements for accuracy, speed, and oversight.

VI. CONCLUSION

LLMs and retrieval-augmented generation represent a new frontier for preservation and access. Our development of a custom RAG pipeline for web archives demonstrates that, with thoughtful optimization, these tools can indeed live up to some of the hype: they can unlock insights from born-digital collections that were previously difficult to obtain, and do so in a manner that keeps the human user in control of verifying and interpreting the results. In the case of our web archives experiment, we showed that an AI-driven conversational search can coexist with the core values of archives (provenance, authenticity, and trust) by systematically grounding each answer in the preserved record.

In this age of uncertainty, where both the digital content we preserve and the tools we use to access it are evolving rapidly, adopting an approach that is both innovative and responsible is key. Our work suggests a few guiding principles: prioritize data quality, prefer open and local solutions where feasible, enforce transparency through citations, and always keep a human in the loop. By doing so, we can harness the power of LLMs to enhance discovery without surrendering our commitment to preservation ethics and scholarly rigor.

The implications of this work extend beyond web archives. Similar RAG pipelines could be applied to other complex collections (oral history transcripts, research data sets, institutional records, personal papers) enabling new forms of inquiry. As libraries and archives explore these possibilities, they must also advocate for and contribute to the development of AI systems that align with preservation needs: systems that are explainable, maintainable, and under the community's control.

Retrieval-augmented LLMs offer a compelling new tool in the preservation and access arsenal. They remind us that preserving information is not just about storing bytes, but also about ensuring that knowledge remains discoverable, verifiable, and usable for future

generations. By carefully integrating AI into our practices, we can navigate the uncertainties of technological change and continue our core mission: to connect people with the knowledge of the past in trustworthy and meaningful ways. The UVic Libraries' RAG pipeline is one example of how we can chart this path: leveraging cutting-edge AI while upholding the principles that define our profession.

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